

Building and Evaluating an Ethernet-based Interconnection Network Prototype using Open-Hardware Designs and FPGAs

Antonio Moran-Munoz^{1*}, Jesus Escudero-Sahuquillo^{1†},
Pedro J. Garcia^{1†}, Francisco J. Quiles^{1†}

¹Computing Systems Department, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha,
Campus Universitario, s/n, 02071 Albacete, Spain.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): antonio.moran@uclm.es;

Contributing authors: jesus.escudero@uclm.es;

pedrojavier.garcia@uclm.es; francisco.quiles@uclm.es;

[†]These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract

The interconnection network is a subsystem evermore important in current Datacenters and supercomputers where data- and computing-hungry applications, used in high-performance computing (HPC), artificial intelligence (AI), or Cloud fields, demand a growing number of communication operations among the server hosts. These demands require that the network subsystem guarantees high communication bandwidth and low latency, otherwise becoming the bottleneck of the entire system. There are numerous interconnection network technologies that are evolving their architectures to accomplish these demands, such as InfiniBand or Ethernet-based networks. In particular, Ethernet-based interconnection networks have improved in the last few years their performance, in terms of latency and throughput, so they have become a competitive and popular choice for Datacenters and Supercomputers. Indeed, there are several open hardware projects, such as Corundum and NetFPGA, which provide interconnection network models that can be implemented in commodity FPGAs. Thanks to these projects the community is contributing to developing novel and efficient network functionalities. In this paper, we describe the process of building an FPGA-based prototype for an Ethernet-based interconnection network. Specifically, we use development boards from the NetFPGA platform, composed of a Xilinx Virtex-7 690T FPGA, internal flash memory, 10GbE transceivers, etc. In these FPGAs, we have implemented open-source designs (NICs and switches) from NetFPGA and Corundum

projects. The cabling of the prototype is flexible so it allows measuring the performance of NIC-to-NIC and NIC-to-switch communication. We have also evaluated several transport protocols (i.e., TCP and UDP) using commonly used benchmarks and tools, and analyzed the different configurations of the software stack to reduce the packet dropping in the communication.

Keywords: Interconnection networks, switch and NIC design, Modeling and prototyping, FPGAs, NetFPGA, Corundum

1 Introduction

With around 95 Zettabytes (ZB) of data generated during 2022 in the global dataspere—and the expected figure of 200 ZB by 2026—the importance of data centers has reached peaks never seen before[1][2]. The success in the business of many big companies, such as Google, Facebook, or Amazon, depends on the proper performance of Data centers. On the other hand, the supercomputing has officially reached the Exascale performance barrier, as the Top500 list has shown in June 2022 for the Frontier Supercomputer, which has achieved 1.102 Exaflop/s of computing performance. In this context of a growing amount of data storage requirements and the unprecedented levels of offered computing power, the application developers are adapting the programming models to leverage the supercomputer and Datacenter architecture.

Nonetheless, the performance requirements of these systems involve certain subjectivity, since not all the applications need the same type of resources in these systems. For instance, some applications will require a network with a very low latency provision—such as streaming services—, while others will be more sensitive to packet loss than to link speed [3]. In order to fulfill the application requirements, the typical elements in these systems that can be designed independently are the processor, memory, and the interconnection network [4], although current design approaches suggest applying co-design practices to design these elements [5].

More precisely, Datacenters and supercomputers consist of a variety of server nodes interconnected through an interconnection network. Indeed, the network subsystem plays a crucial role, as it must guarantee a high communication bandwidth and a low latency to meet the needs of the system applications. Otherwise, the interconnection network will become the bottleneck of the whole system. More precisely, the interconnection network is composed of several devices, such as *network interface cards* (NICs), switches, routers, and links to connect them. Processing and storage nodes are usually provided with one or several NICs that connect these server nodes to the rest of the interconnection network devices (i.e., switches and routers). The protocols and technologies implemented within these devices are diverse, but the recent trend in the Top500 panorama is that Ethernet-based networks are expected to increase its share as new and faster Ethernet variants arise [6].

There are several design issues that have a significant impact on the interconnection network performance, such as the topology, the routing algorithm, device architecture, or the tolerance to packet dropping, among others. Indeed, all these design aspects

should be taken into consideration together, i.e., with a holistic perspective that analyses the impact of new designs on each other aspect. For instance, the design of the network topology influences the routing algorithm, or the offered network bisection bandwidth [7]. Therefore, efficient routing algorithms will need to leverage the network topology properties (e.g., path diversity, bisection bandwidth, etc.).

The flow control between network devices has also imbricated implications with other key aspects in the network design. For instance, the flow control determines the lossless or lossy behavior of an interconnection network. In lossy networks, such as the ones using the UDP transport layer, packets are regularly discarded when switch buffers become full. For instance, this is a common practice in the TCP transport protocols [8], where a retransmission mechanism is implemented to re-send the discarded packets. On the contrary, lossless interconnection networks do not discard packets. Once a packet is injected into the network, it will reach its destination if no dramatic situations happen, such as link failures or power loss. Therefore, the flow control mechanism in lossless networks prevents packet discarding, reducing network latency due to retransmissions with respect to lossy networks. However, flow control introduces head-of-line blocking [9] if the communication operations in the network generate congestion scenarios. Note that in a congestion scenario, the traffic flows will clog the internal network paths, hence the network throughput will drop and the packets latency will skyrocket.

Therefore, network designers must consider all the design aspects when evaluating the functionalities of the new network architectures. Sometimes it is possible to model these functionalities using software-based tools, such as simulators (e.g., OMNeT++ [10], NS-3 [11] or SST [12]) or analytical models [13][14][15], but depending on their abstraction level, the designers may miss certain implications of the proposed designs when moved to real hardware. Therefore, the network simulation-based and/or analytical modeling is usually complemented with hardware-based prototyping (e.g., NetFPGA [16] or Corundum [17]), so that the network designers widen their perspective when analyzing the new functionalities proposed for the network architecture.

Specifically, the NetFPGA project appeared cover the need of a hardware platform aimed to research and experimentation. It achieved it by offering a set open-source network devices programmed in Verilog and configurable on re-programmable hardware. NetFPGA has offered since its inception a wide range of boards and designs with different capabilities, most of them now deprecated¹. The version used in this research is the NetFPGA-SUME which offers both an FPGA board and open-source network devices designs with 10 Gbps capabilities

Despite being a big project back in its day, the NetFPGA community has decayed over the years, affecting the performance and functionality offer by its devices. Nonetheless, other open-source designs have appeared in recent years, being the most significant Corundum's NIC, which offers a high-performance, implementable in a wide range of boards. It also offers extra functionality such as native IEEE 1588 PTP timestamping, support for jumbo frames or a higher performance Linux driver.

¹The most recent version release of NetFPGA is the NetFPGA PLUS, supported by Xilinx Alveo boards

In this paper, we detail the construction of an Ethernet-based interconnection network prototype using open-hardware designs, such as NetFPGA and Corundum, and a set of FPGAs. This prototype will allow us to test new designs and protocols that improve the interconnection network performance. Our main contributions are the following:

- We have configured an Ethernet-based interconnection network prototype using three NetFPGA-SUME boards [18], composed of a Xilinx Virtex-7 690T FPGA, internal flash memory, 10GbE transceivers, etc. Two of these FPGAs implement the NIC design while the third one implements the switch. We use the NIC design developed by the Corundum project² [19] and the switch design offered by the NetFPGA platform (i.e., the reference learning switch) [20].
- We also describe the steps followed to build the prototype: plugging the boards into the computers, synthesis, implementation of the Verilog designs, and FPGAs programming with these designs.
- We have performed a thorough evaluation of the prototype by means of a set of experiments using different acceptance tests and network performance tools, such as *iperf3*, *netperf* and *nuttcp*. The obtained results have allowed us to research the most proper configuration to reduce packet dropping in the transmission between hosts.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides some background on high-performance interconnection networks, as well as some basic concepts about FPGAs, Corundum and the NetFPGA-SUME board, which are necessary for the reader to fully understand the rest of the paper. Section 3 tackles in a precise manner the steps carried out in the construction of the prototype. Section 4 depicts the experiments performed for validating the proper performance of the prototype. Also, an analysis of the obtained results is provided. Finally, in Section 5 the conclusions of this work are detailed.

2 Background

2.1 Interconnection networks

In this section, we describe the basic concepts of interconnection networks. Specifically, an interconnection network is a programmable system that transports data between terminals [21]. As it has been mentioned before, the interconnection network is a key component in supercomputers and Datacenters, since it must guarantee high communication bandwidth and low latency to the communication operations performed by applications running at these systems. If these requirements are not satisfied, then the network becomes the entire system bottleneck, delaying the execution of applications. In recent years, the computing and storage requirements in disciplines such as high-performance computing (HPC), big data, or artificial intelligence (AI), have posed numerous challenges to network designers who have devised a lot of improvements to ramp up the performance of interconnection networks.

²<https://github.com/corundum/corundum>

Essentially, the interconnection network is composed of network interfaces (NICs), switches, and links [22, 23]. The NIC is plugged into the system nodes, usually by means of the PCIe subsystem. The NIC is responsible for splitting application messages into packets and sending/receiving those packets to/from the network. It is very frequent that modern NICs include some direct memory access (DMA) engine, such as *Remote Direct Memory Access* (RDMA) [24], which offloads to the NIC hardware certain communication functionality, whose responsibility is commonly assigned to the CPU. NICs are connected to switches by means of links, which offer different speeds, i.e., the amount of information (i.e., bits or bytes) that they can transport per time unit (i.e., bps or B/s). Currently, the links from some high-performance network technologies, such as InfiniBand or Ethernet, can reach up to 800 Gbps [25, 26].

The switch interconnects NICs or switches to other NICs or switches by means of physical links, so packets can travel throughout the network. Switches are composed of a variety of ports, where packets are received from other switches or NICs. Incoming packets to a switch port are stored in a physical buffer (usually made of SRAM memory), which can be divided into several queues or virtual channels (VCs). After that, the routing unit decides the output port to which every packet needs to be forwarded, and the arbitration and scheduling units are in charge of selecting which packet, among all the ones stored in the switch buffers, can be forwarded through its selected output port. Note that only one packet can cross to that port at a given time instant. Moreover, switches implement in their ports the flow control mechanism, which determines if a packet can be either sent to the next switch or has to be discarded. There are flow control mechanisms that allow packet discarding, which are commonly used in lossy interconnection networks, such as Ethernet. By contrast, there are other flow control mechanisms that do not allow packet discarding, which are commonly used in lossless networks (e.g., InfiniBand, Slingshot, and HPC Ethernet).

Interconnection networks are ubiquitous as they can be found connecting tiny components within a chip or interconnecting cabinets full of servers [4]. For instance, *on-chip networks* (OCNs) usually interconnect components within a chip, such as register files, caches, or IP cores. There are some specifications in this regard, such as ARM’s AMBA, which includes AXI4-Stream and AXI-Lite protocols. It is worthy to mention the AXI4-Stream protocol, as it is widely used in architectures aimed at achieving high performance. It consists of a set of signals that allows for big streams of data to be sent between modules, without the use of addresses to identify those modules. Among the most relevant signals, the following are included:

- **TDATA**. It includes the data to be transferred between modules.
- **TUSER**. It includes metadata information about **TDATA**.
- **TLAST**. It indicates that **TDATA** contains the ending flit of a packet.
- **TREADY**. It indicates that the receiver can receive data.
- **TVALID**. It indicates that **TDATA** contains valid information.

As it is not the purpose of this paper to enter in the details of this protocol, it is enough to say that once a module is ready to receive data, it asserts the **TREADY** signal, indicating the downstream module to send its data through the **TDATA** signal. These protocols are used in both the NetFPGA and Corundum architecture, as we describe later.

Another type of interconnection network is the system area network (SAN), which interconnects processing and storage nodes. Each one of these nodes is provided with a NIC to communicate that node to the rest of the network. Links in this type of network have a length ranging from one meter to a few tens of meters. SANs are the common option for building supercomputers and Datacenters. Indeed, the interconnection network prototype that we present in this paper is an example of a SAN network.

Apart from OCNs and SANs, there are other types of networks that are not commonly used in supercomputers and Datacenters, such as *local area networks* (LANs), which are the most popular ones among commodity users since they are the ones found at home for interconnecting PCs, mobile devices, etc., or *wide area networks* (WANs), which interconnect computers around the globe, covering long distances, so they make possible the existence of the Internet.

2.2 Re-configurable computing hardware

When designing a hardware circuit, we need to consider if this design is going to be implemented in an *application-specific integrated circuit* (ASIC) or a *field-programmable gate array* (FPGA). Even though ASICs are highly efficient and optimized for the task they were made for, their fabrication is very expensive and slow. Moreover, once built, they cannot be reconfigured. By contrast, FPGAs compensate for those drawbacks by offering re-configurable hardware, which is also cheaper in comparison with ASICs. FPGAs allow for the hardware designs to be implemented several times during its development cycle. Also, such a development cycle is shorter than for ASICs. These characteristics make FPGAs perfect devices for research and academia [27] and, in our case, for the development of new high-performance interconnection network architectures.

Currently, despite the presence of several manufacturers, more than three-fourths of the FPGA market share belongs to two companies [28]. The first one is Xilinx, which has been (and still is) the market leader for many years and it was the company that created the first commercially successful FPGA. It was acquired by AMD in 2020 [29]. The second one is Altera, which is Xilinx's main competitor. Also, it was the first company to introduce a re-configurable logic device in the industry. It was acquired by Intel in 2015 [30].

Although an FPGA architecture differs depending on the manufacturer, there are a set of elements common to all of them, such as programmable logic cells, programmable interconnection network, and I/O cells [31].

- **Programmable logic cells (PLC).** Also called *Configurable Logic Blocks (CLB)* in Xilinx devices, these are the components in charge of implementing all the logic of the design defined in the HDL code. Keeping the focus on Xilinx (as it is the FPGA used in the prototype), the CLBs consist of several digital structures properly interconnected to form the basic blocks of Xilinx's FPGAs (see Figure 1): Lookup-Tables (LUT), multiplexers, arithmetic logic, and a storage unit.
- **Programmable interconnection network.** This is the element that allows communication between PLCs. It has to be programmable, as a PLC's functionality

Fig. 1: Basic block of CLBs from Xilinx.

will vary depending on the component implemented in it, and, therefore, the dependencies between modules may differ for each HDL design. The organization of the PLC within the interconnection network is vendor-specific. One of the many FPGA structures is the *symmetrical array* (see Figure 2). Here, the PLBs are arranged as islands in a sea, surrounded by the interconnection network, which runs along the horizontal and vertical axis.

Fig. 2: Symmetrical structure.

- **Programmable I/O.** This component is located in the periphery of the chip (as shown in Figure 2). It allows the FPGA to communicate with external devices. Its programmability allows the configuration of each pin as an input, an output, or a bidirectional pin.

Another important factor to take into account when talking about FPGAs is their power consumption. Although it is true that an ASIC is going to be more power efficient, as its hardware has been tailored for a specific purpose, FPGAs have experienced a reduction in the relative power consumption over the years [32][31].

2.3 NetFPGA project

NetFPGA is an open platform that allows researchers to build their own high-speed networking systems, and teachers to show their students how to build network devices using hardware instead of software. As a result of the NetFPGA’s OpenFlow success, Software Defined Networks gained in popularity [33]. There have been several platforms since NetFPGA’s inception. In fact, NetFPGA-SUME is the third generation of these platforms. As its previous releases, the NetFPGA-SUME platform offers a board and a set of hardware designs that can be synthesized and implemented for its FPGA chip.

The NetFPGA-SUME board is the board included within the NetFPGA-SUME platform. Namely, NetFPGA-SUME is an FPGA-based x8 Gen3 PCIe board with I/O capabilities for 10 and 100 Gbps operation. The FPGA included in the board is the Xilinx’s Virtex-7 690T [34]. In detail, the NetFPGA-SUME board consists of the following main components [35]:

- **Xilinx Virtex-7 690T FPGA.** It is a chip optimized for high-performance applications and contains 693,120 logic cells and a 52,920 Kb block RAM.
- **Host interface.** It is an 8x lane PCIe 3.0 interface with a bandwidth of 8Gbps per lane, which is used to connect the development board to a host PC.
- **Front panel ports.** There are four external SFP+ ports with 10 Gb Ethernet capabilities each one.

Also, the NetFPGA-SUME platform supports different open-source network device designs, such as switches, NICs, or routers. The synthesis of the different network device designs is possible thanks to a script-based infrastructure written in `tc1`, interpreted by the Xilinx Vivado IDE. Figure 3 represents the block diagram for the datapath of the *reference learning switch* design, available in the NetFPGA repositories. Data enters the switch through one of its four input ports and is immediately forwarded into the input arbiter module. Here, the packets will wait until it is selected by the arbitration unit (that follows a *Round-Robin* policy) to be forwarded to the output port lookup module. In this module, the destination is chosen by looking up at a content addressable memory (CAM). Once the destination is set, the packet exits the switch through the corresponding port. Every module within the datapath is interconnected via AXI-Stream, whose most representative signals are shown in the diagram. So if, for instance, an input port wants to send a packet (TDATA) to the corresponding FIFO queue from the input arbiter, it will have to wait until the TREADY

signal is asserted. TUSER is another signal that includes metadata information such as the destination and source addresses.

Fig. 3: Block diagram of the reference learning switch.

2.4 Corundum project

Corundum is an open-source, high-performance NIC design with a capability of up to 100 Gbps per port. Apart from being a more up-to-date design compared to the one implemented by the NetFPGA-SUME platform, it has support for a wider range of boards than the NetFPGA-SUME board. Among its features are the following: “a high-performance datapath (i.e., 10G/25G/100G Ethernet), PCI express gen 3, a custom, high performance, tightly-integrated PCIe DMA engine, many (1000+) transmit, receive, completion, and event queues, scatter/gather DMA, MSI, multiple interfaces, multiple ports per interface, per-port transmit scheduling including high precision TDMA, flow hashing, RSS, checksum offloading, and native IEEE 1588 PTP timestamping” [36].

This project also provides a Linux driver and several development and debugging tools. All of these, added to the high modularity of the design, make this a perfect platform for in-network computing as new modules can be added to the base architecture.

Figure 4 shows the Corundum architecture. Among the most representative modules, we can distinguish the following [37]:

- **Interface.** This module implements the interface of the NIC, including functionality such as the queue management logic, descriptor, completion, and event handling, transmit scheduler, and the transmit and receive datapaths.
- **RX/TX.** These modules implement the datapaths for the reception and transmission of packets, respectively. They include a RX/TX engine and an ingress/egress module.
- **Ingress/Egress.** These modules are included within the previous ones and they are in charge of processing the incoming/outcoming packets.

In the same way that it occurred with the NetFPGA datapath, these internal modules that make up the data-plane engine of the NIC, are interconnected via AXI-Stream, as it allows the fastest data transfer possible between modules. These

high-level blocks are implemented through a set of Verilog modules that describe the functionality already indicated.

Fig. 4: Block diagram of the Corundum NIC.

3 Prototype Description

In this section, we describe the Ethernet interconnection network prototype. Firstly, in Figure 5 we can see a diagram of the prototype, consisting of three hosts: two of them (i.e., Host A and Host B) have the FPGAs configured with the Corundum NIC design, while the third one (i.e., Switch) has the FPGA configured with the switch design. The hosts are connected in two ways: using a fiber cable from the *nf3* interface at host A to the host B *fpga0* interface, and using two interfaces both at Host A and B connected to the four switch interfaces.

The first step to building the prototype is to carry out the physical connection of the NetFPGA-SUME boards to the PCIe 3.0 slot in the PC motherboard and the optical-fiber cables to the SFP+ ports of the NetFPGA-SUME board (see Figure 6).

The following steps are the synthesis and the programming of the network component designs into the FPGA (both the NICs and the switch), the PCIe and network driver configuration in the hosts, and the operating system’s parameter *tuning* in order to obtain the best performance when using the prototype. In the following subsections, we describe these steps.

3.1 Synthesis and programming of the network designs

In this section, we describe the synthesis and implementation of the designs in the FPGA, according to the Corundum and NetFPGA-SUME documentation [38][39]. As stated before, these are two independent open-source projects, developed in Verilog HDL. Prior to performing the synthesis of the projects, it is needed to install the Xilinx tools (Vivado and Vitis) as they will be used under the hood to perform the whole process. Once those software tools are installed, the synthesis of both designs is automated by scripts. To launch them, it is necessary to go to the corresponding directory and run a `make` command that takes care of the several steps required to synthesize and implement the design. Figure 7 shows the commands needed to begin

Fig. 5: General overview of the FPGA-based prototype.

the synthesis process. As Corundum supports several boards, it is important to go to the NetFPGA-SUME directory, as it is the board that we will be using.

In the case of the switch design, the process requires a few steps more. The first step is to make the cores in the root directory of the NetFPGA-SUME project (see Figure 8).

Because the reference learning switch from NetFPGA-SUME makes use of CAM tables to take care of the switching mechanism, it is necessary to make the CAM and TCAM cores prior to the synthesis. Before compiling them, we have to download the *xapp1151_Param_CAM.zip* module and copy it in the corresponding folders. Figure 9 shows the full steps in order to make these cores.

After all the cores have been made, we have to go to the switch design directory and run another `make` command that launches the synthesis and implementation of the switch (see Figure 10).

After generating the *bitfile* of a given design, we need to program the FPGA to use it. Although there are two ways of programming the FPGA³ (JTAG port or flash) we will use the flash slots, as they will store the *bitfile* in the NetFPGA board and, each time the board turns on, such *bitfile* will be automatically retrieved to program the FPGA. In this way, there is no need to program the FPGA board manually each time a host is turned on, and there is no need to plug the JTAG cable to program the FPGA each time the host is turned on.

³Programming mode is selected via the *JP1* jumper in the NetFPGA board.

(a) Board attachment to PCIe 3.0 x8.

(b) Cable connection.

Fig. 6: Ping test results for the two prototype configurations.

```
cd <path-to-corundum>/fpga/mqnic/NetFPGA-SUME/fpga/fpga
source /tools/Xilinx/Vivado/2020.2/settings64.sh
make
```

Fig. 7: Commands to run the synthesis and implementation of the Corundum NIC design.

```
cd <path-to-netfpgasume>
make
```

Fig. 8: Making the cores of NetFPGA-SUME design.

To program the NetFPGA card, we have used two methods. The first one is using Digilent's Adept 2 tools. Figure 11 shows the two options for the `dsumecfg` command (each one with different parameters) that we have used to program the FPGA. In the first option, `dsumecfg` writes the indicated *bitfile* in one of the four available flash slots. In the second option, `dsumecfg` tells the board which one of the slots needs to

```

# Copying the zip files in the corresponding directories
(for CAM core)
cp xapp1151_Param_CAM.zip <path-to-netfpgasume>/lib/hw/xilinx/cores/cam_v1_1_0/
or
(for TCAM core)
cp xapp1151_Param_CAM.zip <path-to-netfpgasume>/lib/hw/xilinx/cores/tcam_v1_1_0/

# Making the cores
(for CAM core)
cd <path-to-netfpgasume>/lib/hw/xilinx/cores/cam_v1_1_0/

(for TCAM core)
cd <path-to-netfpgasume>/lib/hw/xilinx/cores/tcam_v1_1_0/

make update      # decompress the .zip file
make sim         # simulate the cores
make             # compile the cores)

```

Fig. 9: Making the CAM and TCAM cores of switch design.

```

cd <path-to-switch-directory>
make

```

Fig. 10: Synthesis and implementation of the switch design.

be selected to retrieve the *bitfile*. Obviously, it has to be the same slot where the *bitfile* was written to.

```

dsumecfg write -d <device-name> -s <slot-number> -f <bitfile-name>

dsumecfg setbootsec -d <device-name> -s <slot-number>

```

Fig. 11: Flash configuration using *dsumecfg*.

Figure 12 shows the output result of using the *dsumecfg* commands to program the NetFPGA.

After these steps, the FPGAs of the prototype will be configured with the NIC and switch designs whenever they boot. Nonetheless, this approach was not suitable for the switch design, as it has a proprietary module whose usage when implemented expires after eight hours. After these eight hours, the FPGA has to be reconfigured. Thus, for configuring it, the *xsct* tool was used. After launching this tool from the terminal, the *tcl* commands are shown in Figure 13. For this method to work, the NetFPGA-SUME board has to be connected via JTAG cable to the host computer. Otherwise, the *connect* command will fail.

It is important to note that these two methods work for the NetFPGA-SUME boards, but may not (and probably will not) work for more modern and powerful boards.

3.2 Network interfaces configuration

Once the FPGA is programmed, we need to configure the hosts' network interfaces. The first step is to compile both the *mgnic* and the *sume-riffa* drivers [38][40]. After

```

anon@anon:~/pCloudDrive/Universidad/TFM/Bitfiles$ dsumecfg write -d NetSUME -s 0 -f reference_nic_VLAN_enabled_shared_v1.9.0.bit
Configuring FPGA...
FPGA configuration succeeded.
Erasing Flash: 100%
Writing Flash: 100%
Configuration Successfully Written to Flash
anon@anon:~/pCloudDrive/Universidad/TFM/Bitfiles$ dsumecfg setbootsec -d NetSUME -s 0
Configuring FPGA...
FPGA configuration succeeded.

```

Fig. 12: Bitfile storage in the NetFPGA flash memory using *dsumecfg*.

```

connect
fpga -f <bitfile-name>.bit

```

Fig. 13: Configuring the FPGA with *xsct*.

that, it is necessary to include the compiled driver in the list of modules that the operating system (OS) kernel uses. We have installed the Ubuntu 22.04 OS in the three nodes of the prototype. Next, we need to perform the network interface configuration at each one of the hosts. Note that this configuration depends on the OS version installed. In our case, for the Ubuntu 22.04 OS, the configuration is done via the *netplan* tool. Table 1 shows a summary of the interface configuration in each host.

Table 1: Overview of the network interfaces configuration.

Host	Interface	IP address	MAC address
A	eth0	192.168.3.10/24	Random
	eth1	N/A	N/A
	eth2	N/A	N/A
	eth3	N/A	N/A
B	eth0	192.168.3.20/24	Random
	eth1	N/A	N/A
	eth2	N/A	N/A
	eth3	N/A	N/A

It is important to highlight that the hosts A and B of the prototype need to have the RIFFA driver available and the network interfaces configured, according to the values from Table 1, so there can be connectivity among the network devices implemented in the FPGAs that are part of the prototype.

3.3 Operating System Tuning

To improve the operation of the prototype, the last step is to tune some parameters in the operating system (OS) kernel, namely, the buffer size. Being some of the traffic used for testing connection-less (UDP), the offered performance of the prototype might be lower than expected, and could even be the cause of connection interruptions between the hosts. Therefore, it is advisable to properly configure certain kernel variables to obtain the best performance possible out of the prototype. Figure 14 shows the kernel variables configured in the */etc/sysctl.conf* file. These are the variables related to the socket buffer. For instance, if we increase the default size of the read and write

buffers used in network connections from 208 KB to 50 MB, then the socket buffers should be less prone to overflow situations.

```
# Read buffer
sysctl -w net.core.rmem_default= <buffer-size>
sysctl -w net.core.rmem_max= <buffer-size>

# Write buffer
sysctl -w net.core.wmem_default= <buffer-size>
sysctl -w net.core.wmem_max= <buffer-size>
```

Fig. 14: Kernel buffer size configuration.

4 Experiments and results

In this section, we describe the experiments performed to test the operation of the prototype and to achieve the best performance. We also provide a discussion on the observed performance among the different tools used and the different values of the kernel buffer.

4.1 Experiments Configuration

Figure 15 shows an extended diagram of the prototype, summing up its basic information, that is, the IP addresses assigned to each interface in the NIC. This figure also depicts two different configurations defined to perform different experiments, as we describe later.

Specifically, these configurations are the following:

- **Configuration 1.** Direct connection from one NIC port at host A to another one at host B. The NIC design is the one belonging to Corundum.
- **Configuration 2.** Indirect connection between NICs, through the switch with a *Round-Robin* (RR) arbitration unit. This is the default reference learning switch design.

The experiments carried out are intended to evaluate three key aspects of the prototype: the proper operation of the board, the existence of a connection between hosts, and the performance of the prototype. More precisely, the experiments performed to evaluate the prototype are the following:

- **Acceptance test.** This suite of tests is included in the NetFPGA-SUME repository alongside the designs and the simulation/compilation infrastructure. It consists of a set of individual tests, each of which evaluates the proper operation of each subsystem of the NetFPGA board. In our case, it is only necessary to run the *10G Loopback* test, which checks that the *nfX* interface from the board correctly works at the physical level.
- **Ping experiment.** It verifies the connectivity between the interfaces of hosts A and B. Despite the simplicity of the test, it is a crucial one since no connectivity means that there is an issue with the network driver and/or the interface configuration.

Fig. 15: Extended prototype diagram, that shows the IP address from each network interface and the three established configurations.

- **Performance experiments.** For these experiments, a set of network performance tools have been used. Namely, `iperf3`, `netperf`, and `nuttcp`, which let us measure the throughput of configurations #1 and #2 of the prototype. Some of the tools are more powerful or have more options than others, but the three of them let us evaluate the most important parameter of the configurations, the throughput.
 - *iperf3*. The `iperf3` is a tool for performing network throughput measurements and allows us to generate both TCP and UDP traffic so that we can perform measurements with a connection-oriented communication and a connectionless one.
 - *Netperf*. The `netperf` tool is a benchmark that is used to measure various aspects of networking performance. With this tool, we are able to make tests varying the message size. It allows the generation of TCP and UDP streams too.
 - *nuttcp*. The `nuttcp` is a tool whose most basic usage is to determine the TCP, or UDP, network layer throughput. It allows also the measurement of the RTT of the connection.

It is important to note that these experiments have been automatized by means of a set of scripts that run several instances of these software tools extracting the average results from all those instances, as well as the throughput from the individual runs as will be explained later on.

4.2 Acceptance test and ping results

This test can be run by going to the corresponding folder of the NetFPGA-SUME project (`<NetFPGA-SUME-root-directory>/projects/acceptance_test`). Before launching the application with the `make test` command, it is necessary to build the IP cores with the `make cores` command [41]. Specifically, we need to run the *10G Loopback* test, which needs to be successful to demonstrate that both the 10G Ethernet ports and the optical fiber cables are up and running. Regarding the `ping` command, Figure 16 shows the output results for the three prototype configurations.

```
antonio@hosta:~/corundum/modules/mqnic$ ping 192.168.0.20
PING 192.168.0.20 (192.168.0.20) 56(84) bytes of data.
64 bytes from 192.168.0.20: icmp_seq=1 ttl=64 time=0.845 ms
64 bytes from 192.168.0.20: icmp_seq=2 ttl=64 time=0.670 ms
64 bytes from 192.168.0.20: icmp_seq=3 ttl=64 time=0.612 ms
```

(a) Configuration #1: Host A - Host B.

```
antonio@hosta:~/corundum/modules/mqnic$ ping 192.168.0.20
PING 192.168.0.20 (192.168.0.20) 56(84) bytes of data.
64 bytes from 192.168.0.20: icmp_seq=1 ttl=64 time=0.894 ms
64 bytes from 192.168.0.20: icmp_seq=2 ttl=64 time=0.668 ms
64 bytes from 192.168.0.20: icmp_seq=3 ttl=64 time=0.693 ms
```

(b) Configuration #2: Host A - Switch - Host B.

Fig. 16: Ping test results for the two prototype configurations.

As we can see, there is connectivity for the evaluated scenarios. This means that the FPGA board is properly configured, the `mqnic` PCIe driver is up and running, and the IP address configuration of the network interfaces is correct.

4.3 Performance experiments results

The goal of this set of experiments is to measure the link throughput for the two prototype configurations and for different kernel buffer sizes.

As we said before, we use three software tools, which are run within a bash script. This script sets the kernel buffer size to six different values. The sizes chosen are: 104 KB, the default one of 208 KB, 512 KB, 1 MB, 10 MB and 50 MB. The script then launches 50 instances of each tool and takes the average value of different metrics for later use. The main metric measured is the throughput, as it is the main one and common to all three tools. We have also measured other metrics that were offered by some of the tools, such as the datagram loss for UDP traffic, which is calculated by some of the tools (i.e. `iperf3` and `nuttcp`). We have made different graphs and comparisons between different tools that will be described in the corresponding sections.

Moreover, we have kept track of the throughput value for each one of the 50 runs of the different tools, both for TCP and UDP traffic. With the data, a series of box-and-whisker plots have been made in order to see the distribution of the different runs and check the stability of the different configurations. The logic behind this is to test the variability between runs and check if the configurations are stable over time runs.

4.3.1 iperf3 results

For this test, we use `iperf3` as a server in Host B and as a client in Host A. On the client side, there are several options included in the `iperf3` call that indicate whether the traffic is TCP or UDP, and also to modify the *bitrate* at which the traffic is sent from the source. For TCP traffic, the bitrate option has been left out, as by default it injects the maximum bitrate possible into the connection. In the case of UDP traffic, different tests have been made for different injection bitrates because we are interested in the point at which the connection begins to overflow and packets start to drop.

Figure 17 shows the commands used to launch the client, either with TCP or UDP traffic. We performed the tests for 11 seconds each, omitting the first second (`-0` option) because the control packets of the communication altered a little bit the throughput measurements. Also, we have printed the result in Mbps (`-m` option).

```
# TCP traffic
iperf3 -c <SERVER_IP> -B <CLIENT_IP> -01 -t <TEST_DURATION> -f m

# UDP traffic
iperf3 -c <SERVER_IP> -B <CLIENT_IP> -u -b <bitrate>M -01 -t <TEST_DURATION> -f m
```

Fig. 17: Commands for iperf3 client. A value of 0 in `-b` option indicates no limit in the bitrate injection.

In Figure 18 are shown the two box-and-whisker plots obtained from the TCP runs for both configurations. Figure 18b shows the results obtained for configuration #1, while Figure 18a does the same for configuration #2. As it can be seen, configuration #1 shows perfect stability, as the three “Qs” are equal among every buffer size and there are not any outliers. On the contrary, configuration #2 shows how certain runs, for every buffer size, underperformed. Apart from reaching a throughput lower than configuration #1, there is more variability between runs. These results suggest that the switch is responsible for the poorer overall performance of the TCP connection in `iperf3`. Also, increasing the buffer size reduces the number of outliers and yields higher quartiles, which means higher overall throughput among the 50 runs.

Tables 2 show the results obtained for every buffer size when the `iperf3` tool is configured to send TCP traffic. The results for the six buffer sizes are grouped within both configurations. In this case, apart from the throughput, the average number of retransmissions that took place during the tests is included.

As we can see, configuration #1 achieves an average throughput value higher than configuration #2. Regarding the number of retransmissions taking place during the tests, the number of retransmissions with the default buffer size is noticeably superior to that of the increased buffer size. These results seem to indicate that, in configuration #2, the switch could be acting as a bottleneck, increasing the number of

Fig. 18: iperf3 TCP boxplots for the two prototype configurations.

retransmissions which in turn decreases the throughput of the connection. In fact, this performance is not encountered in configuration #1 where there is no such switch. With respect to the different buffer sizes, there is not a remarkable difference between any of the measured metrics, so it is not something that has any impact in the TCP communication. This makes sense, as TCP is a connection-oriented protocol that aims to negotiate a set of parameters between the hosts in order to provide a stable and reliable connection.

Table 2: iperf3 TCP traffic average link throughput.

Buffer size	Configuration	Throughput (Mb/s)	Retransmissions
104 KB	#1	9415.000	0
208 KB	#1	9415.000	0
512 KB	#1	9415.000	0
1 MB	#1	9415.000	0
10 MB	#1	9415.000	0
50 MB	#1	9415.000	0
104 KB	#2	8451.360	8587.060
208 KB	#2	8458.240	8781.000
512 KB	#2	8441.540	8728.700
1 MB	#2	8457.020	8748.180
10 MB	#2	8465.360	8738.480
50 MB	#2	8466.500	8753.120

Regarding the UDP traffic, Figure 19 shows the corresponding box-and-whisker plots for UDP traffic, namely when no injection limit is applied to the communication.

(a) Configuration #1: Host A - Host B. (b) Configuration #2: Host A - Switch - Host B.

Fig. 19: iperf3 UDP boxplots for the two prototype configurations.

In this case, both configurations show a great performance as the buffer size gets bigger. In fact, when the buffer size is 50 MB, we can see that there are almost no outliers and the quartiles are very close together. Moreover, the throughput obtained for configuration #1 is slightly higher than that of configuration #2. On the other side, when the buffer size is lower than the default value (i.e. 104 KB), throughput decays below 9000 Mbps. Therefore, we can say that the default buffer kernel value is enough to achieve almost full bandwidth, though it is a more unstable connection (especially for configuration #2) as there are several runs away from the median values. Also, we can say that the 10 MB buffer size marks the point at which both connections gain in stability as the outlier values are greatly reduced.

The results shown in Table 3 summarize the throughput values obtained for an iperf3 UDP communication with no injection bitrate limit. It shows the values obtained for different buffer sizes for both configurations. From this table, we can see that the values obtained for configuration #1 are slightly better. But it is more remarkable the datagram loss reduction in configuration #1. This suggests that the switch is affecting the connection. A striking thing is that the datagram loss for the biggest buffer size is higher. This may be explained because the client can send traffic to its buffer at a higher rate than the NIC can send it to the network. Therefore, all this traffic starts to be dropped. This does not happen with other buffer sizes because, by getting overflowed before, they do not allow the client to send an amount of data to its own buffer.

Regarding the packet dropping observed in the different experiments for UDP traffic, we have analyzed this rate for the different prototype configurations and different injection bitrates of *iperf3*. Note that UDP is a connectionless transport protocol and it does not provide, by default, any end-to-end flow control mechanisms. Moreover, the

Table 3: iperf3 UDP traffic average link results when there is no injection bitrate limit.

Buffer size	Configuration	Throughput (Mb/s)	Datagram loss (%)
104 KB	#1	8525.560	.301
208 KB	#1	9117.140	.257
512 KB	#1	8648.180	.302
1 MB	#1	9132.140	.267
10 MB	#1	9399.000	.340
50 MB	#1	9501.780	6.006
104 KB	#2	8601.400	.263
208 KB	#2	8635.140	.701
512 KB	#2	9371.740	.668
1 MB	#2	9187.460	.766
10 MB	#2	9344.160	.725
50 MB	#2	9462.220	8.522

hardware designs with which the FPGA boards are programmed also miss a link-level flow control mechanism, so packet dropping will occur in certain circumstances.

Fig. 20: Percentage of discarded packets in UDP traffic generated with *iperf3* varying the injection *bitrate* (0 means there is no limitation in the bitrate).

Figure 20 shows a graph summing up the results obtained for UDP traffic using an increasing number of injection bitrates and two buffer sizes, i.e., 104 KB and 50 MB. Note that this experiment does not make sense for TCP since there is no packet dropping when using this transport protocol. In the case of 104 KB buffers (i.e., the left-hand side graph), configuration #1 shows that there is a certain packet loss for every injection bitrate. Nonetheless, the results shown are a bit misleading because, as can be seen, for lower injection bitrates, datagram loss is way higher than when there

is no limit in the injection bitrate. This may occur because of the way `iperf3` works when sending UDP traffic (cite <https://github.com/esnet/iperf/issues/386>). `iperf3` sends UDP datagrams in a bursty way, that is, it interweaves idle periods where it does not send any datagram, with busy/bursty periods. When the injection bitrate is lower, these bursty periods are less frequent but very intense. What may be happening in this case is that during the bursty periods, the injection bitrate surpasses the NIC’s capability to send these data into the network and, in consequence, overflows the buffer. This is mitigated when the buffer size is increased, as seen in the Figure, because such a buffer can hold more datagrams before it overflows.

In the case of 50 MB buffers, we can see a similar trend, being the lower injection bitrates the more lossy. Nonetheless, the loss is less remarked because of the bigger buffer size. The great loss when there is no limit in the injection bitrate was explained previously when analyzing the results seen in Table 3.

Finally, it is worth mentioning again that the packet dropping is produced by the lossy nature of the FPGA-based network in our prototype. Note that the NetFPGA switch and Corundum NIC designs do not include link-level flow control (neither credit-based nor Stop-and-go-based). The “congestion control” seen is at the application level, because of `iperf3` not being able to send data to a congested buffer. As a future work, we plan to implement this functionality in the Verilog code of the output queue modules both at NIC and switch FPGA designs.

4.3.2 Netperf results

With `netperf` we have made throughput measurements. The instructions performed on the client side are shown in Figure 21. The main difference with respect to the `iperf3` is that here, for UDP traffic, we have made throughput measurements for different message sizes.

```
# TCP traffic
netperf -H <SERVER_IP> -l <TEST_DURATION> -t TCP_STREAM -f m

# UDP traffic
netperf -H <SERVER_IP> -t UDP_STREAM -l <TEST_DURATION> -- -m <msg-size> -- -f m
```

Fig. 21: Commands for `iperf3` client. A value of 0 in `-b` option indicates no limit in the bitrate injection.

Figure 22 shows the corresponding TCP traffic box-and-whisker plots for the `netperf` tool. Here, we can see similar results to those obtained with the `iperf3` tool, but in this case, the configuration #1 shows a little more instability, showing some outliers in the left-hand side graph. In the case of configuration #2, the communication behaves similarly to `iperf3`, underperforming for every buffer size.

In Table 4 we can see the average throughput values obtained from the 50 TCP runs using the `netperf` tool.

For every buffer size, the throughput is very similar. What we can appreciate, though, is the influence of the switch in it. In both tables, the throughput obtained in configuration #1 is higher than configuration #2, the same way that happened with `iperf3` (we could not gather retransmission information with `netperf`, though). This

Fig. 22: netperf TCP boxplots for the two prototype configurations.

Table 4: netperf TCP traffic average link throughput.

Buffer size	Configuration	Throughput (Mb/s)
104 KB	#1	9411.305
208 KB	#1	9412.973
512 KB	#1	9341.928
1 MB	#1	9250.498
10 MB	#1	9262.006
50 MB	#1	9391.364
104 KB	#2	8458.740
208 KB	#2	8455.973
512 KB	#2	8358.571
1 MB	#2	8367.610
10 MB	#2	8415.998
50 MB	#2	8462.132

suggests that the switch is having a negative impact on the communication. This seems to corroborate the hypotheses that the switch affects TCP's negotiation parameters leading to a poorer performance.

For UDP traffic, a comparison between the different message sizes has been made. Figure 23 shows the box-and-whisker plots for buffer size 104, while Figure 24 shows the corresponding results for a buffer size of 50 MB.

In the left-hand side of Figure 23 are compared the boxplots obtained when the buffer size is 104 KB. Except for a message size of 512B, the rest of the sizes reach a high throughput. Nonetheless, there is a high variability too, with many outliers and wide boxes when the message size is higher. We see, that this variability is slightly

(a) Configuration #1: Host A - Host B. (b) Configuration #2: Host A - Switch - Host B.

Fig. 23: netperf UDP boxplots for buffer size of 104 KB.

(a) Configuration #1: Host A - Host B. (b) Configuration #2: Host A - Switch - Host B.

Fig. 24: netperf UDP boxplots for buffer size of 50 MB.

worsened a little bit in configuration #2, as the right-hand side shows wider boxes and more extreme outliers.

When the buffer size is increased to 50 MB, we see that the panorama changes. Figure 24 shows much slimmer boxes, with almost no variability between runs. The bigger size allows also the throughput to be higher for a 16 KB message, which it was not possible with the 104 KB buffer size. Regarding the configurations, no appreciable differences are seen in throughput.

Figure 25 shows two graphs (one for each buffer size) that compare the different throughput values obtained for different message sizes.

Fig. 25: Throughput in UDP traffic generated with *netperf* varying the message size.

On the one hand, we see that the overall throughput increases when the buffer size is 50 MB, which makes sense as the server side can hold bigger quantities of data. On the other hand, for each message size, configuration #1 offers a very slightly better performance than configuration #2, but the difference is almost negligible.

4.3.3 nuttcp results

With *nuttcp* we have made the same measurements that have been made with the *iperf3* tool in order to see if there is any influence on the performance of the tools. The instructions to run on the client side are the ones shown in Figure 26. The options in this case are the same used with the *iperf3* tool, so we will be able to make a comparison between them and check if the software used has any influence on the performance.

```
# TCP traffic
nuttcp -i1 -T <TEST_DURATION> <SERVER_IP>

# UDP traffic
nuttcp -u -Ri<bitrate>m -i 1 -T <TEST_DURATION> <SERVER_IP>
```

Fig. 26: Commands for *iperf3* client. A value of 0 in *-b* option indicates no limit in the bitrate injection.

As we did with *iperf3* and *netperf*, we begin by studying the boxplots obtained after the 50 runs performed with the tool.

(a) Configuration #1: Host A - Host B. (b) Configuration #2: Host A - Switch - Host B.

Fig. 27: nuttcp TCP boxplots for the two prototype configurations.

In this case, in Figure 27 we can see that, the same way it happened with the two previous tools, configuration #1 outperforms configuration #2 in both throughput and stability. Thus, we can conclude that the NetFPGA-SUME switch has an impact on TCP connections.

Tables 5 summarize the average values of the TCP communication metrics measured by the nuttcp tool, which are the same as those of the iperf3 tool.

Table 5: nuttcp TCP traffic average link throughput.

Buffer size	Configuration	Throughput (Mb/s)	Retransmissions
104 KB	#1	9406.345	0
208 KB	#1	9406.396	0
512 KB	#1	9406.361	0
1 MB	#1	9406.349	0
10 MB	#1	9404.909	0
50 MB	#1	9406.421	0
104 KB	#2	8451.360	0
208 KB	#2	8458.240	0
512 KB	#2	8441.540	0
1 MB	#2	8457.020	0
10 MB	#2	8465.360	0
50 MB	#2	8466.500	0

The values for the throughput are almost the same for both tools, but in `nuttcp` there are no retransmissions. This may be due to the fact that the protocol implementation is different in these tools or, even, because of the differences in the interaction of the tools with the underlying operating system.

In the case of UDP traffic, we can see the boxplot results in Figure 28. For `nuttcp` the throughput results are more packed together as it happened with `iperf3` and `netperf`. Nonetheless, in this case, the throughput values do not surpass 9000 Mbps, as it happened with `iperf3`.

Fig. 28: `nuttcp` UDP boxplots for the two prototype configurations.

Tables 6 show the average throughput values obtained from the 50 runs for every configuration and buffer size. As we can see in the boxplots, the performance is lower than 9000 Mbps. This worse performance may be due to the way the tools work with UDP traffic. While `nuttcp` uses a default message size of 64 KB, `iperf3` dynamically adjusts the message size for a better performance.

Lastly, Figure 29 shows the corresponding `nuttcp` graphs comparing the datagram loss in UDP traffic for different bitrates. In this case, datagram loss is almost non-existent at any injection bitrate. This may be caused because of the way `nuttcp` works, too. While `iperf3` invalidates a whole measurement when control packets get lost, `nuttcp` does not [42].

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we have described the process to build and evaluate an FPGA-based interconnection network prototype, using the NIC designed by the Corundum project

Table 6: *nuttcp* UDP traffic average link results when there is no injection bitrate limit.

Buffer size	Configuration	Throughput (Mb/s)	Datagram loss (%)
104 KB	#1	5174.920	.235
208 KB	#1	8080.292	.442
512 KB	#1	8253.948	.417
1 MB	#1	8288.786	.449
10 MB	#1	8303.546	.423
50 MB	#1	8045.803	.460
104 KB	#2	5701.107	.253
208 KB	#2	8144.499	.523
512 KB	#2	8193.372	.477
1 MB	#2	8371.146	.451
10 MB	#2	8351.956	.463
50 MB	#2	8266.549	.493

Fig. 29: Percentage of discarded packets in UDP traffic generated with *nuttcp* varying the injection *bitrate* (0 means there is no limitation in the bitrate).

and the switch provided by the NetFPGA-SUME platform. Our prototype is composed of three hosts: two of them being attached to a NetFPGA-SUME board implementing Corundum, and the third one attached to another NetFPGA-SUME board implementing the 4-port NetFPGA-SUME switch. We have used optical-fiber cables to connect the two NICs directly and with the switch in the middle, so we can evaluate the direct and indirect communication. We have detailed in the paper the main steps carried out for the connection and configuration of the different prototype components. Moreover, we have performed a set of experiments for the different prototype configurations, to test that the prototype elements are up and running and connection exists between every network device. We have also measured the effective link bandwidth used by

different traffic patterns generated by different tools, and based on the TCP and UDP transport protocols. As the interconnection network in the prototype is lossy, we have analyzed the percentage of dropped packets in the case of UDP using different values of certain OS kernel parameters involved in the network communication. Also, we have studied the variability of the multiple executions performed during the tests, in order to assess whether the connection is stable or not. According to the results obtained, we can conclude that the intermediate switch destabilizes the communication, offering an overall worse performance than direct communication between the hosts. Although it is reasonable that an intermediate step in the communication deteriorates the performance, the impact of the switch is quite high as it reduces the throughput by around 11%. Although this prototype represents the most simple interconnection possible, it will serve as the basis for the future evaluation of new hardware designs that will be included in the FPGA boards. In fact, we are currently working on implementing a flow-control mechanism called Priority-based flow control (or PFC) that allows us to reduce the UDP datagram loss for high injection bitrates. Also, as a future work, the plan is to scale the prototype to include enough FPGAs to make a bigger interconnection network that allows us to perform more interesting traffic patterns that could have a bigger impact on the network.

Acknowledgements

This work has been jointly supported by the UCLM with a pre-doctoral contract 2020-PREDUCLM-14816, corresponding to the pre-doctoral contracts for research staff in the frame of the Internal Research plan of R+D+i, co-funded by the European Social Fund (ESF) (UCLM Resolution of 15/06/2020); and Xilinx University Program, thanks to the donation of two Alveo boards U55C. Also, this work has been jointly supported by the Spanish Ministry of Science MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033, and the European Commission with the Project Grant TED2021-130233B-C31 (NextGenerationEU/PRTR), and by Junta de Comunidades de Castilla-La Mancha with the project SBPLY/17/180501/000498.

References

- [1] Patrizio, A.: IDC: Expect 175 zettabytes of data worldwide by 2025. [Online; accessed Sep. 24, 2021]. <https://www.networkworld.com/article/3325397/idc-expect-175-zettabytes-of-data-worldwide-by-2025.html>
- [2] Vopson, M.M.: The world's data explained: how much we're producing and where it's all stored. <https://theconversation.com/the-worlds-data-explained-how-much-were-producing-and-where-its-all-stored-159964>. [Online; accessed Sep. 24, 2021]
- [3] Ceran, E., Çilden, E., Gültekin, E., Canberi, M.H.: Network packet loss sensitivity analysis for symques codec. In: 2018 26th Signal Processing and Communications Applications Conference (SIU), pp. 1–4 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/SIU.2018.8404555>

- [4] Hennessy, J.L., Patterson, D.A.: Computer Architecture, Fifth Edition: A Quantitative Approach, 5th edn., pp. 2–4. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., San Francisco, CA, USA (2011). Chap. F
- [5] ERNST, R., HENKEL, J., BENNER, T.: Hardware-software cosynthesis for microcontrollers. In: Micheli, G.D., Ernst, R., Wolf, W. (eds.) Readings in Hardware/Software Co-Design. Systems on Silicon, pp. 18–29. Morgan Kaufmann. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-155860702-6/50004-1> . ISSN: 18759661. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9781558607026500041>
- [6] Platform, N.: The Eternal Battle Between InfiniBand and Ethernet in HPC. <https://www.nextplatform.com/2021/07/07/the-eternal-battle-between-infiniband-and-ethernet-in-hpc/>. [Online; accessed Sep. 29, 2023] (2021)
- [7] Kaplan, F., Tuncer, O., Leung, V.J., Hemmert, S.K., Coskun, A.K.: Unveiling the interplay between global link arrangements and network management algorithms on dragonfly networks. In: 2017 17th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing (CCGRID), pp. 325–334 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCGRID.2017.93>
- [8] Sinyov, N., Olenev, V., Lavrovskaya, I., Korobkov, I.: Research and analysis of flow control mechanism for transport protocols of the space wire onboard networks. In: 2016 19th Conference of Open Innovations Association (FRUCT), pp. 219–225 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.23919/FRUCT.2016.7892204>
- [9] Karol, M., Hluchyj, M., Morgan, S.: Input versus output queueing on a space-division packet switch. IEEE Transactions on Communications **35**(12), 1347–1356 (1987) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCOM.1987.1096719>
- [10] Bautista, P.B., Urquiza-Aguiar, L.F., Igartua, M.A., Reinoso-Chisaguano, D.J., Paredes-Paredes, M.C.: An evaluation of omnet++-based v2x communication frameworks: On the path towards 5g-v2x simulations. In: Proceedings of the 24th International ACM Conference on Modeling, Analysis and Simulation of Wireless and Mobile Systems (MSWiM '21), pp. 75–78 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3479239.3485723>
- [11] Kumar, A.R.A., Rao, S.V., Goswami, D.: Ns3 simulator for a study of data center networks. In: 2013 IEEE 12th International Symposium on Parallel and Distributed Computing, pp. 224–231 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISPDC.2013.37>
- [12] Hsieh, M., Riesen, R., Thompson, K., Song, W., Rodrigues, A.: Sst: A scalable parallel framework for architecture-level performance, power, area and thermal simulation. The Computer Journal **55**(2), 181–191 (2012) <https://doi.org/10.1093/comjnl/bxr069>

- [13] Willick, D.L., Eager, D.L.: An analytic model of multistage interconnection networks. In: Proceedings of the 1990 ACM SIGMETRICS Conference on Measurement and Modeling of Computer Systems (SIGMETRICS '90), pp. 192–202 (1990). <https://doi.org/10.1145/98457.98758>
- [14] Torrellas, J., Zhang, Z.: The performance of the cedar multistage switching network. *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems* **8**(4), 321–336 (1997) <https://doi.org/10.1109/71.588598>
- [15] Javadi, B., Abawajy, J.H., Akbari, M.K.: A comprehensive analytical model of interconnection networks in large-scale cluster systems. *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience* **20**(1), 75–97 (2007) <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.1222>
- [16] al., N.Z.: Netfpga sume: Toward 100 gbps as research commodity. *IEEE Micro* **34**(5), 32–41 (2014) <https://doi.org/10.1109/MM.2014.61>
- [17] Forench, A., Snoeren, A.C., Porter, G., Papen, G.: Corundum: An open-source 100-gbps nic. In: 2020 IEEE 28th Annual International Symposium on Field-Programmable Custom Computing Machines (FCCM), pp. 38–46 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/FCCM48280.2020.00015>
- [18] NetFPGA: NetFPGA SUME. [Online; accessed May 26, 2022]. <https://netfpga.org/NetFPGA-SUME.html>
- [19] Forench, A., Snoeren, A.C., Porter, G., Papen, G.: Corundum: An open-source 100-Gbps NIC. In: 28th IEEE International Symposium on Field-Programmable Custom Computing Machines (2020)
- [20] Galea, S.: NetFPGA SUME Reference Learning Switch. [Online; accessed Sep. 29, 2023]. <https://github.com/NetFPGA/NetFPGA-SUME-public/wiki/NetFPGA-SUME-Reference-Learning-Switch#name>
- [21] Dally, W.J., Towles, B.P.: Principles and Practices of Interconnection Networks, p. 2. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., San Francisco, CA, USA (2004). Chap. 1
- [22] Duato, J., Yalamanchili, S., Lionel, N.: Interconnection Networks: An Engineering Approach. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., San Francisco, CA, USA (2002). Chap. 1
- [23] Segura, P.Y.: New queuing schemes to improve the efficiency of hybrid and hierarchical high-performance interconnection network topologies. PhD thesis, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha (2018). <http://hdl.handle.net/10578/19674>
- [24] Guo, C., Wu, H., Deng, Z., Soni, G., Ye, J., Padhye, J., Lipshteyn, M.: Rdma over

- commodity ethernet at scale. In: Proceedings of the 2016 ACM SIGCOMM Conference (SIGCOMM '16), pp. 202–215 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2934872.2934908>
- [25] Corporation, N.: NVIDIA MMS4X00-NM 800Gbps Twin-port OSFP 2x400Gb/s Single Mode DR8 500m. <https://docs.nvidia.com/networking/display/mms4x00nm800g500m>. [Online; accessed Oct. 15, 2023]
- [26] Cisco: Cisco ASR 9902 Compact High-Performance Router. <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/products/collateral/routers/asr-9000-series-aggregation-services-routers/datasheet-c78-744663.pdf>. [Online; accessed Oct. 15, 2023]
- [27] Hauck, S., DeHon, A.: Reconfigurable Computing: The Theory and Practice of FPGA-Based Computation. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., San Francisco, CA, USA (2007)
- [28] HardwareBee: List of FPGA Companies. [Online; accessed May 27, 2022]. <https://hardwarebee.com/list-fpga-companies/>
- [29] Trimberger, M. Stephen: Three ages of fpgas: A retrospective on the first thirty years of fpga technology. Proceedings of the IEEE **103**(3), 318–331 (2015) <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2015.2392104>
- [30] HardwareBee: Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) History. [Online; accessed May 27, 2022]. <https://hardwarebee.com/field-programmable-gate-array-fpga-history-applications/>
- [31] Bobda, C.: Introduction to Reconfigurable Computing: Architectures, Algorithms and Applications, (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-6100-4>
- [32] Klein, M.: Power consumption at 40 and 45 nm. (2009). <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:13938050>
- [33] Zilberman, N., Dudziak, L., Jadczyk, M., Parks, T., Rietmann, A., Safronov, V., Zuo, D.: Cut-through network switches: architecture, design and implementation. Technical Report UCAM-CL-TR-928, University of Cambridge, Computer Laboratory (November 2018). <https://doi.org/10.48456/tr-928> . <https://www.cl.cam.ac.uk/techreports/UCAM-CL-TR-928.pdf>
- [34] marcinwoj: Home. [Online; accessed Sep. 24, 2021]. <https://github.com/NetFPGA/NetFPGA-SUME-public/wiki>
- [35] Zilberman, N.: P51: High Performance Networking. [Online; accessed May 26, 2022]. <https://www.cl.cam.ac.uk/teaching/1819/P51/lab1.pdf>
- [36] Forencich, A.: Introduction. [Online; accessed Sep. 29, 2023]. <https://docs>.

[corundum.io/en/latest/](https://docs.corundum.io/en/latest/)

- [37] Forencich, A.: Modules. [Online; accessed Oct. 14, 2023]. <https://docs.corundum.io/en/latest/modules/index.html>
- [38] Forencich, A.: Getting Started. [Online; accessed Sep. 9, 2023]. <https://docs.corundum.io/en/latest/gettingstarted.html>
- [39] Nicolau, C.: Hardware Tests. [Online; accessed May 26, 2022]. <https://github.com/NetFPGA/NetFPGA-SUME-public/wiki/Hardware-Tests>
- [40] KastnerRG: riffa. [Online; accessed Jun. 13, 2022]. <https://github.com/KastnerRG/riffa>
- [41] Galea, S.: Acceptance Test Project. [Online; accessed Jun. 13, 2022]. <https://github.com/NetFPGA/NetFPGA-SUME-public/wiki/Acceptance-Test-Project>
- [42] Felix: Measuring throughput in wireless networks: iperf vs nuttcp. <https://fjrk.net/measuring-throughput-in-wireless-networks-iperf-vs-nuttcp/>. [Online; accessed Oct. 15, 2023]